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THE PURSUIT OF GREAT ENGINEERING COURSES. DIVE INTO A STAFF DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM AND REACH THE TOP?

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In the recently started special interest group (SIG) on Capacity Building, we noticed that teacher qualification requirements differ between countries and, sometimes, even between universities in the same country. Based on this observation, we arranged a workshop during the annual SEFI meeting in September 2021, asking participants for up-to-date information about requirements in their diverse national and institutional contexts and could learn about best practises from each other. Most of participants were from Europe (11), but Australia (1) and the United States (1) were also represented.

HOW IS PEDAGOGICAL TRAINING ARRANGED?

The discussion was lively: several interesting points were raised regarding how pedagogical training is arranged in different contexts. For example, in Twente (the Netherlands), university lecturers are required to have university teaching qualification (~100h) focusing on pedagogy, assessment, and pedagogical technology. In Finland, there is a difference between universities of applied sciences, where all lecturers are required to have pedagogical competence (60cr), and traditional universities, where pedagogical training is not obligatory. In Sweden, a pedagogical portfolio and the attendance at pedagogical courses are required to become a "qualified teacher" and finally an "excellent teacher". One participant from London (United Kingdom) wrote: "We've worked to create an environment in our institution where education is valued and rewarded, which persuades staff to take

part”). However, in many places, pedagogical training possibilities and/or requirements are missing or just start to emerge.

Interestingly, in many technical universities, pedagogical training is organized at the institutional level. Such a format makes it possible to concentrate on discipline-specific pedagogical training, but it misses the opportunity to talk across totally different disciplines, like humanistic fields or social and health care. At Umeå University (Sweden), pedagogical training is provided by a pedagogical development centre, but lecturers from all departments are invited to co-teach pedagogical development courses. The aim of this approach is to build capacity for decentralized capacity-building, that is, lecturers learn how to train other lecturers and can thus help their home departments in local pedagogical development. In Finnish universities of applied sciences, capacity building is provided at vocational teacher training colleges. Those colleges bring together teachers from all parts of Finland and from different disciplines (technology, business, social and health care etc.). Pedagogical training is part of these studies. Most of the workshop participants reported that participating in pedagogical training does not give any reduction in teaching load, meaning that all pedagogical studies must be done at one’s own time. Sweden is an exception, where pedagogical training can be done as part of a given allotment of “competence development time” that all lecturers are entitled to. However, most lecturers prefer using that time for research rather than pedagogical training.

IDEAS FOR IMPROVEMENT

Pedagogical studies and training are a key in developing engineering education. The combination of theory and practical training is a main element in learning, also in pedagogical training. A participant from Twente (the Netherlands) mentioned that they experience that teaching quality (at least among newer teachers) has increased since requirements for pedagogical training were implemented. Unfortunately, there is no research yet to support this experience. No matter whether there are requirements for teaching qualification or not, none of the participants reported on continuous pedagogical development requirements during lecturers’ careers. Notifying the rapid change in possible or necessary teaching practises (COVID-19!), progression with pedagogical training would open eyes for e.g., new technological possibilities.

We also note that, if participating in pedagogical studies does not lead to a reduction in teaching load, it is very understandable that lecturers may be reluctant to participant in these activities, especially if they are optional. There are so many things one must learn at the early stages of a career, that optional studies are not the first thing in the mind. However early teaching experiences may influence how one approaches teaching later in one’s career and early pedagogical training could therefore be particularly beneficial. Participants also raised the idea of developing a standard qualification or even a European certificate for capacity building for higher education lecturers, but this question needs to be discussed further.

CONCLUSION

During the conference we heard several keynotes and panels focusing on future skills of engineers. All of these presentations emphasised continuous learning, technical knowledge, and working online. We argue that future engineers will not be able to reach these skills if the teaching staff is not encouraged (or required?) to develop these skills themselves.

Figure 1. Map of participants in the workshop